

A framework for sustainability assessment-based Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO): A case study of building sector in Mexico

Pedro Maximiliano Cortez Lara, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico
31.01.2024

Keywords: *Building and construction, sustainability assessment, Multifunctional Analysis of Region through Input-Output, MARIO, Mexico, Input-Output analysis*

Fundings

This publication was supported by Climate Change Growth (CCG), World Bank Group (WBG), and 2050 Pathways Platform. Its contents are solely the responsibility of the author and do not necessarily represent the official views of the CCG, WBG and 2050 Pathways Platform.

Acknowledgements

This report was created during the Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and the Caribbean (EMP-LAC) 2024 organized by the Climate Corporate Growth Programme. The author would like to thank Anna Vinciguerra and Lorenzo Rinaldi from Politecnico di Milano for his constructive feedback during the drafting of the manuscript.

Executive Summary

Historically, building and construction sectors have played a significant role in the development of national economies all over the world. There is evidence that building, and construction (B&C) sectors plays a pivotal role in determining quality of life and is a key contribution determinant of cultural identity and heritage. However, over the last 30 years this sector has been the subject of several studies due to the high environmental impact. This paper present an adaptative framework based on Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO) in Mexico for environmental assessment. The study presents calculation of greenhouse and heavy metal emissions, and its relationship to health hazards. The result shows that the proposed framework has the potential to easily be implemented and the capability to assess all types of sectors. Furthermore, it provides a promising alternative for integral sustainability assessment for regions with lack of tools.

1. Introduction

Since 1970, the energy crisis and global warming have caused significant problems for all developed and developing countries (Geng et al., 2019). Building and construction (B&C) sectors are important components in the economies of the countries and plays a key role in climate change. Since 1990's, the B&C sector has been recognized as a highly environmental impact industrial sector (Haapio & Viitaniemi, 2008). Extensive research has shown that B&C contributes to 40% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Ibn-Mohammed et al., 2013), 50% of energy and consumption resources (Dixit, 2017), 30% of wastewater production (Pomponi & Moncaster, 2016), and 15% of drinking water usage (Baynes et al., 2018). Furthermore, data from several studies have shown that only concrete global production is responsible for 9% of water withdrawals (Pomponi & Stephan, 2021).

Throughout the last years, the research efforts have primarily focused on in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approaches. Countries all over the world have developed more than 600 assessment methods to evaluate environmental impact in Building sector for different

categories and study areas such as water, materials and resources, energy, circular economy, and adaptation to climate change (Doan et al., 2017). Overall, these studies suggest the urgent need to explore different approaches to assess sustainability impact in the B&C sectors.

This paper presents an adaptative framework that serves to evaluate the effects of B&C sectors based on Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO) (Tahavori et al., 2023). Hence, the main innovation of this study can be summarized as follows:

- To provide a new approach for sustainability assessment using local data using MARIO.
- To serve as a route for future Input-Output sustainability assessment research.

2. Methodology

Data availability

Currently, there is a compatibility limitation between Insituto Nacional de Estadística, Geografía e Informática (INEGI) Mexico database and MARIO analysis tools. In order to develop assessment-based MARIO, dataset from EXIOBASE 3 was used in this study. EXIOBASE 3 is an open-access data base which provides a time series of environmental extended multi-regional input-output (EE MRIO) tables ranging from 1995 to a recent year for 44 countries (Stadler et al., 2021).

Materials and methods

The presented study proposes a framework for sustainability assessment using Input-Output (I-O) in MARIO. MARIO base methods provides a means of a holistic calculation of multifunctional analysis of regions in open- Python and Excel Environment. Furthermore, it compiles MRIO, LCA-IO, Circular Economy, and Supply-Use Tables (SUT) handling for an all-in-one analysis. The calculation domains are (1) greenhouse gases emissions, (2) heavy metal production, and (3) health hazards due to GHG. The results of the environmental assessment are later sorted, filtered, and plotted. The entire framework is presented in Fig. 1.

The framework consists of 4 modules to assess sustainability impact in accordance with ISO 15392: Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works – General principles. The process begins with the Preliminary Work module by compiling and reviewing the needed information to build the database. Afterwards, a set of parameters are selected and linked to the IO matrices. If the dataset lacks information to perform analysis, MARIO allows to create new parameters to evaluate its behavior in the study region. Subsequently, data is collected and sorted to be processed through the matrices calculation for multifunctional analysis (e.g. shock and multiple scenarios analysis) Finally, data information is exported to .txt and .xlsx file for planning and assessment of the industry sector.

Fig. 1. Flowchart for environmental assessment-based MARIO

3. Results

To assess the difference between the calculate values with MARIO, a table was generated for the study period (Append A) and Person correlation (CI: 0.95) were plotted domain (Append B). All the analysis processes were carried out on a Windows 11 Home 64-bits OS, Intel i5 CPU 2.7 GHz processor and 8.00 GB RAM personal computer.

All calculated GHG and heavy metal emissions produced by B&C sector are presented in Fig. 2. The single most striking observation to emerge from data comparison from Fig. 2a, 2b and 2c and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPPC) was the similarity of values. This is a rather significant outcome from the presented approach using I-O analysis with MARIO for GHG calculation.

Fig.2. GHG and heavy metal analysis emissions by B&C sectors from 1995 to 2022.

Further statistical analysis tests presented in Table 1 revealed all the correlations between B&C and the rest of the sectors. Interestingly, the more surprising correlation is with the Treatment sector. This is a remarkable outcome and indicated an urgent need to develop new strategies for waste management and treatment in the B&C sector.

TABLE 1. PEARSON CORRELATION (CI:0.95) ANALYSIS OF CALCULATED SECTORS

	Construction	Agricultural	Oil and Gas	Mining	Food processing	Energy	Other industries
Agricultural	0.979						
Oil and gas	0.975	0.998					
Mining	0.901	0.919	0.916				
Food processing	0.983	1.000	0.998	0.918			
Industry	0.986	0.999	0.997	0.919	1.000		
Energy	0.976	0.999	0.995	0.917	0.999		
Other industries	0.980	1.000	0.998	0.918	1.000	0.999	
Treatment	0.145	0.152	0.171	0.134	0.152	0.143	0.153

Fig. 3 provides the intercorrelations among carbon dioxide emissions and built houses in Mexico from 1995 to 2020. It is apparent from Fig 3, that CO₂ emissions occurred with successive increases in built houses. Fig. 4 presents an overview of correlations between heavy metals air pollution and cancer deaths. According to (Kim et al., 2015) , almost all

heavy metals are serious toxicants as carcinogens. Results from Fig.4 demonstrated a correlation between number of cancer deaths caused by heavy metals pollution. This result must be interpreted with caution because it only analyzes the effect of the B&C sectors. However, MARIO calculates all the I-O matrices to develop a comprehensive analysis of multiple scenarios using data from all the industry sectors. Additional research is needed to better understand the relationship between the B&C sector and the health sector.

Fig 3. Carbon dioxide emissions relationship with built houses in Mexico

Fig 4. Heavy metal air pollution relationship with cancer death in Mexico

4. Discussion

Collectively, the proposed framework has the ability to effectively calculate environmental values for sustainability assessment. The systematic structure and MARIO environment for calculating introduces simplicity for the sustainability assessment in the environmental, economic, and social areas. The framework is especially useful for intra-regional analysis in countries using I-O matrices. Conventional techniques for sustainability assessment tend to focus only in the building sector as energy modeling software, environmental LCA for building and materials, environmental assessment frameworks and rating systems, and environmental guides or checklists for building design and management. Thus, the

proposed framework offers a simple and practical approach using standardized I-O tables for any required sector. However, extensive datasets are required for every country to analyze and plan strategies for the future. Furthermore, more research is required to study the behavior of new sectors and identify potential risks towards sustainability.

5. Conclusion

The presented framework for sustainability assessment-based MARIO was developed to fill the gap of B&C sectors using ISO 15392 as reference standard. The approach was implemented and tested for the B&C industry of Mexico. The study performed an entire calculation of I-O matrices using EXIOBASE 3 and INEGI databases. The results of this research support the idea that the framework present an easier alternative to assess sustainability with a high degree of simplicity. A limitation of this study is the compatibility between MARIO I-O and INEGI templates. Future studies should be realized to compile and produce INEGI database using MARIO template for a deeper analysis in Mexico. Furthermore, it is necessary to investigate and create a complete dataset to understand the effects and relationships between supply, commodities, sectors, value added, and satellite accounts.

References

- Baynes, T. M., Crawford, R. H., Schinabeck, J., Bontinck, P.-A., Stephan, A., Wiedmann, T., Lenzen, M., Kenway, S., Yu, M., Teh, S. H., Lane, J., Geschke, A., Fry, J., & Chen, G. (2018). The Australian industrial ecology virtual laboratory and multi-scale assessment of buildings and construction. *Energy and Buildings*, 164, 14–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.12.056>
- Dixit, M. K. (2017). Life cycle embodied energy analysis of residential buildings: A review of literature to investigate embodied energy parameters. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 79, 390–413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.051>
- Doan, D. T., Ghaffarianhoseini, A., Naismith, N., Zhang, T., Ghaffarianhoseini, A., & Tookey, J. (2017). A critical comparison of green building rating systems. *Building and Environment*, 123, 243–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2017.07.007>
- Geng, Y., Ji, W., Wang, Z., Lin, B., & Zhu, Y. (2019). A review of operating performance in green buildings: Energy use, indoor environmental quality and occupant satisfaction. In *Energy and Buildings* (Vol. 183, pp. 500–514). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.11.017>
- Haapio, A., & Viitaniemi, P. (2008). A critical review of building environmental assessment tools. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 28(7), 469–482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2008.01.002>
- Ibn-Mohammed, T., Greenough, R., Taylor, S., Ozawa-Meida, L., & Acquaye, A. (2013). Operational vs. embodied emissions in buildings—A review of current trends. *Energy and Buildings*, 66, 232–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2013.07.026>
- Kim, H. S., Kim, Y. J., & Seo, Y. R. (2015). An Overview of Carcinogenic Heavy Metal: Molecular Toxicity Mechanism and Prevention. *Journal of Cancer Prevention*, 20(4), 232–240. <https://doi.org/10.15430/JCP.2015.20.4.232>
-

- Pomponi, F., & Moncaster, A. (2016). Embodied carbon mitigation and reduction in the built environment – What does the evidence say? *Journal of Environmental Management*, 181, 687–700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.08.036>
- Pomponi, F., & Stephan, A. (2021). Water, energy, and carbon dioxide footprints of the construction sector: A case study on developed and developing economies. *Water Research*, 194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2021.116935>
- Stadler, K., Wood, R., Bulavskaya, T., Södersten, C.-J., Simas, M., Schmidt, S., Usubiaga, A., Acosta-Fernández, J., Kuenen, J., Bruckner, M., Giljum, S., Lutter, S., Merciai, S., Schmidt, J. H., Theurl, M. C., Plutzar, C., Kastner, T., Eisenmenger, N., Erb, K.-H., ... Tukker, A. (2021). EXIOBASE 3. *Industrial Ecology and Sustainability Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3583070>
- Tahavori, M. A., Rinaldi, L., & Golinucci, N. (2023). Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8308515>

Append A

TABLE A1. GHG EMISSIONS CALCULATED FOR B&C INDUSTRY USING THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK.

	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015	2022
Carbon Dioxide (Mt CO ₂ -eq)	26,972.85	46,415.30	57,730.11	69,960.98	86,976.28	71,939.95
Methane (Mt CO ₂ -eq)	112.72	169.21	206.82	241.83	310.13	300.35
Nitrous Oxide (Mt CO ₂ -eq)	109.18	234.58	332.19	476.54	603.23	419.30
Cement production (Mt CO ₂ -eq)	7,947.70	11,651.83	13,882.36	14,016.77	15,781.05	15,056.71
Built houses	19,412,123	21,954,733	24,706,956	28,643,491	31,949,709	35,233,462

TABLE A2. HEAVY METAL EMISSIONS CALCULATED FOR B&C INDUSTRY USING THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK.

	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015	2022
Arsenic (As)	11.28	15.41	18.19	19.69	23.07	19.02
Cadmium (Cd)	0.80	1.13	1.35	1.45	1.71	1.50
Chromium (Cr)	1.17	1.69	2.22	2.36	2.79	3.02
Copper (Cu)	14.98	22.82	28.25	39.99	46.95	51.45
Mercury (Hg)	0.59	0.84	1.12	1.19	1.46	1.35
Niquel (Ni)	24.23	33.42	28.01	18.53	16.81	15.59
Lead (Pb)	2.23	3.53	5.22	5.75	7.36	8.33
Selenium (Se)	1.73	2.70	5.03	4.93	6.42	6.47
Zinc (Zn)	8.59	14.49	17.03	20.75	25.53	29.65

Append B

Fig. B1. Pearson correlation (CI:0.95) analysis of calculated sectors

